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**YOUNG CONSUMER BASED AUTHENTICITY: NEW OPPORTUNITIES
FOR TERROIR PRODUCT? AN EXPLORATORY APPROACH**

**LE JEUNE CONSOMMATEUR ET LA QUETE DE L'AUTHEMTCITE : DE
NOUVELLES OPPORTUNITES POUR LE PRODUIT DE TERROIR ? UNE
APPROCHE EXPLORATOIRE**

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RESUME

Peu de recherches se sont intéressées à la question de l'authenticité marchande perçue des jeunes consommateurs. En s'appuyant sur le paradigme de la consommation postmoderne, ce travail vise à explorer l'authenticité du produit de terroir autant qu'un concept mobilisateur d'un engouement de la part des jeunes consommateurs. Pour cela, nous mobilisons une étude qualitative exploratoire auprès de 20 consommateurs marocains. Nous montrons que les jeunes étudiés possèdent des critères spécifiques à l'authenticité, et cette recherche ne se limite pas dans le produit matériel mais elle renvoie à un dialogue intergénérationnel sous diverses conditions. La compréhension de cette quête postmoderne représente un apport à considérer par les coopératives dans leur segmentation et communication.

MOTS CLES :

Authenticité perçue, jeunes consommateurs marocains, postmodernisme, coopératives Souss Massa.

ABSTRACT

Few studies have addressed the question of the perceived market authenticity of young consumers. Building on the postmodern consumption literature, the focus of this analysis is on exploring the relationship between young people and the authenticity of local products of the Souss Massa region. Our topic question is: to what extent does authenticity influence the behaviour of young Moroccan consumers? For this, we use qualitative approach based on 20 interviews with Moroccan consumer. We show that the young people studied have specific criteria for authenticity, and this research is not limited to the material product alone but refers to an intergenerational dialogue under various conditions. Understanding this postmodern quest is a contribution that cooperatives need to consider in their segmentation and communication.

KEY WORDS:

Perceived authenticity, young Moroccan consumers, postmodernism, Souss Massa cooperatives

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INTRODUCTION

Young people ' consumption has been regarded as a part of postmodernism paradigm. According to (Maffesoli, 2000), the majority of contemporaries show a particular attention to the original thing. The postmodern sociology mobilizes the local area as a dominant framework (Cova and Cova, 2002). This consumption is presented more than the purchase's act, which is a search for self, credibility, and connection with the past (Trilling 1973, Camus, 2007). Current consumption is looking up for a rather particular dialogue with product. In this regard, the rapprochement between generation and postmodernity would be relevant for our analysis, because according to several studies, daily life is lived from near or far as an inheritance from previous generations (Curasi and al., 2004). This is the aim of this research.

This paper reports on an empirical study of the connection between terroir product and quest of authenticity. We use this line of inquiry through the semi-directive interviews were conducted to understand the background of the young Moroccan's quest for authenticity. This rapprochement aims to question the continuity of this reflection over time, since these young people will be future consumers (Vermeir and Verbeke, 2008).

1. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

1.1. THE NATURE OF GENERATION IN MARKETING

Generation is a polymorphic notion that has been attributed to different meanings. Indeed, in business research generation has been dialed with four meanings in different studies (Table 1). The first focuses on the issue of family transmission, by studying the mutual learning and influence within the family (Curasi and al., 2004; Ladwein et al., 2009). The second addresses age groups referring to individual time, which has been widely used in the segmentation and to understand consumption's practices (Lambert-Pandraud and al., 2005). The third focuses on cohorts to define their behavior's consumption. Cohorts refer to the experience for the same age group at an event at the same frequency, the effect of the time, (Rentz and Reynolds, 1980). As for the fourth stream, it studies cohorts from the perspective of generational markers, no longer based on demographic time but on collective, social or historical time (Arsenault, P. M., 2004; Noble and Schewe, 2003). We can summarize these different indicators as follows:

Table 1: the acceptances of generation in Marketing.

Generation's criterion	Determinants	Study's goals
Age, Years	Individual, biological time	Understanding and classification of behaviors
Demographic cohorts	Effect of time	
Generational cohorts	Collective marker (historical, social)	
Familial exchange	Learning and transmission of practices	The study of interaction between different generation

Source: authors

The sociological and socio-cognitive approach of generation (Attias-Donfut, 1991) has been widely used in marketing research. This approach claims to value the political, economic, and historical context as well as the shared values of consumption (Noble and Schewe, 2003). Generational markers would allow an understanding of time influenced by generational changes (Strauss and Howe, 1998; Prel, 2000; Chauvel, 2006). Recent marketing research has highlighted the importance of studying the behaviour of generations by comparing quantitative criteria (date of birth, chronological age, etc.) and qualitative criteria (common events, collective time, transmission of practices, etc.) (Ladwein et al., 2009; Bourcier-Bequaert, 2010; Lorey et Albouy, 2015). Thus, consumption values could be interpreted from the perspective of generational chorotes. First, the consumer went through a period of acquisition of standards that lasted until he or she became active (Noble and Schewe, 2003), after, several choices were available: maintain, negotiate or abolish those behaviors (Ladwein et al., 2009). This sociological approach to the generation meets the objectives of our paper's research. Indeed, the quest for authenticity is one of the major characteristics of contemporary consumption. We are witnessing a time when consumption would show several changes from its old paradigm. In the following lines, we mobilize the quest for the authentic as a feature of the consumption of the current generation.

1.2. THE QUEST FOR POSTMODERN AUTHENTICITY

Although their differences, postmodernism's contributions in business studies could not be neglected. In marketing, several studies have elucidated the influence of postmodernity on different aspects of consumption and behaviour in general (Camus, 2002; Cova and Cova, 2002a, 2002b; Dholakia and Firat, 2003; Bergada 2008). The characteristics of this consumption have been reduced by Cova and Cova (2002a) to three main dimensions: institutional, sacred and social, which idealize

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postmodern consumption under a search for authenticity. Over this last years, we are witnessing a return to local and original thing (Cova and Cova 2002b), motivated by a strong (Live, 2010), relative and contradictory imagination (Firat and Venkatesh, 1995). This literature claims that the postmodern customer would be willing to liberate himself from ideals and release in his behaviour a certain contradiction and inconsistency. In this context, we would acknowledge that, faced with traditional home groups, he would no longer take responsibility, he sets his own consumption rules to satisfy his imagination, thus requiring to understand his determinants of the search for authenticity. More and more, this quest could also be linked to the pure intention of the producer/seller. Since the authentic has been represented by something beyond the market sphere, stakeholders at the time of the exchange should interact by vocation and not market intent (Goulding, 2000). All in all, the use of authenticity in Marketing does not escape several complexities, which is why researchers recommend that it be studied for a specific research object and context.

At this stage of research, we will try to understand the link between young consumers on the one hand, and the quest of authenticity in the context of local products on the other. We adopted an interpretive paradigm. The purpose of the study is therefore to answer the following question: to what extent does authenticity influence the behaviour of young Moroccan consumers? Thus, we specify that we do not wish to position ourselves for a specific clan of postmodern paradigm but we have mobilized it as a source of reflection in order to try to understand the quest for the authentic as one of the consumption's features of the postmodern age.

2. METHODOLOGY

Qualitative research method

The choice of young Moroccan consumers

We were interested in young Moroccans for their important places in current consumption. They will be consumers of tomorrow. Thus in this phase, they negotiate their childhood-inherited choices, in a postmodern era, which has not been sufficiently studied in a Moroccan context to our knowledge.

Data collection

An exploratory qualitative approach was carried out in April 2018. The 20 interviewees were randomly recruited according to the principle of saturation of responses. We have satisfied a diversification in age, socio-professional categories and lifestyle. As for lifestyle, we believe that after leaving their families, they would be able to decide on consumption and make their choices. Thus, autonomy is an important criterion for understanding an individual's consumption choices because he or she dictates his or her own behavior (Maunaye, 2001).

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Data analysis

As we aim to clarify and develop understanding of young's perception of terroir product authenticity, we have chosen a qualitative research approach. To meet our objective, we opted for a thematic analysis of the content, which is mainly comprehensive and involves several readings of the full interviews in order to understand them (Thompson and. al 1990). The core steps in our analysis of qualitative data consist of: coding the data, organizing the codes into categories and themes, and interpreting the results (Sinkovics et al. 2005).

Our line of inquiry was about these questions: terroir product's origin, ancient manner of preparing terroir product, authenticity's ingredients, authenticity's consumption and the digital's role for this consumption. The interviews lasted between 20 and 35 min. Indeed, we started by completely rewriting the recorded interviews, which were then divided and grouped into thematic units. The results of this work of verbatim analysis are presented in the following lines.

3. FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Provenance of the product

The indication of origin has been related to the perception of authenticity and its valorization. Food products with a known history, care made and geographical indication are spontaneously cited as examples of authentic products (Camus, 2004). The mention of the origin of terroir products is a core criterion for BUSINESS authenticity: "to ensure the authenticity of a product, I try to find out where it comes from, personally, I do not feel comfortable by buying argane from a cooperative that does not belong to Souss!"(N°W9); " Argane is the core product and the most popular one in our region, that's why I always inquire the mention the village of cooperative, it's the origin of the raw material" (N°M1); "For me, lately I often buy the products during a public exhibition because it reassures me about its origin, this represents for me a guarantee of everything I seek in a terroir product, because I have lost contact with a trust person" (N°M6). In general, our results are consistent with those of others researches in different contexts (Sylvander B. and Lassaut B., 1992; Camus, 2004; Bergadaà, 2008). However, in a Moroccan context, the way this provenance is sought is distinct: "the best way to ensure origin is: my hand, touch, (laughs), personally I am not very aware of labels" (N°M2); "the origin of the local product is important, that's why I always bring it with me from my mother, she do it by a high care (N°W12). We can explain this less consideration of the label or institutional identification by the nature and number of the label displayed on the product. In this logic, labeling remains a question of valuation that is difficult to control, as it could lead to an information overload (Sirieix et al., 2013),

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especially since the positive effect between the label and the actual act of purchase is not always systemic (Janssen and Hamm, 2012; Larceneux et al., 2012).

Old manner asked by young people

Ancestral production's manner is a core component of the young' quest for authenticity. "I check the smell, the color and ask for information on the way of production, just to make sure that product has what I learned ,for example, from my family" (N°M6); "I don't hide anything from you, I consume the terroir product because, our ancestral did not suffer from such the recent diseases, and this is due to the nature of their consumption... they consumed old, natural and simple things, so I seek the old behind such consumption" (N°M2). Also, the question of modernizing or modifying the way of production in order to satisfy the adepts of modernity can be asked. "Some time I ask for modifications to the product before delivery: lanterns with light bulbs and not candles, sometimes even a perfect finish of the object..." (N°M8); " I'm less often looking for the old with the new, actually I don't always asked it, especially if this request concerns a very old and inherited thing" (N°W12); " I think that the old is always asked, except that sometimes cooperative has to make known the qualities of this old, and sell it, and not to easily follow the technology, if not, their product would look like a simple local product, and not a very authentic one" (N°W1); " I remember that a craftsman has refused to do modification in his product, not because he doesn't aware of it but because he wants to remain faithful to his origins "(N°M7). These results are different from those of Bergadàa (2008) who realized that the feeling of nostalgia is less present than the improvement of procedures. We would argue that this difference lies in the purpose of the research and the profile of the interviewees. We have been interested on consumers who are not necessarily very aware of production processes and their improvements. Thus, the relationship with the origins is always maintained except that sometimes a customer can expect a small modification in order to gain the facility "I sometimes ask for a black glass jar, or a custom color a little modern for them, but for me, it is just to have a unique thing" (N°W11), or make it modern but in moderation "I want an old product certainly, but also a packaging easy to use and economical for use" (N°F10). This demand for opposites in a single product refers to one of the major characteristics of postmodern consumption: the cohabitation of contradictions in a one need (Firat and Venkatesh, 1995).

Look for an imaginary

As discussed, literature has often linked the quest for authenticity to a quest for the imaginary. Furthermore, sometimes this research could be guided by different criterion to the basic definition of authenticity. This imagination would refer to the local or\ and natural thing (Cova and Cova, 2002).

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Consumers surveyed appreciate a product that reminds them of specific events, situations or moments in their childhood. "The taste of argane for example is linked, for me, to the moments shared with the family... that's exactly what I'm looking for" (N°M8); "I qualify it as authentic only if this product takes something old, that I met during my childhood because I come from this region..." (N°W7). Thus, this feedback is directly cited by young consumers and they like to hear about it. "I like to know the true procedures and ways of our ancestors, certainly, our period is quite developed but there are things that should not change too much... we buy it to find the past, the classic that holds several virtues and also it is recommended by my parents." (N°M8). "I eat the authentic for my health, and my physical and psychological well-being ... recently, we are very attentive to what is happening lately on the environmental level....thing are hazardous enough than previously" (N°W5). These clarifications explain the results of Cova and Cova (2002) who attested that postmodern would be described as a fairly important, difficult and not necessarily unique quest for authenticity.

Online community's role.

The young people consulted show a core presence of the digital in their daily lives. Their ways of consuming would become an expression to be shared. "When I enjoy, I share, and when I'm disappointed I also share... I often stay connected to my online family " (N°W6); "yes, I ask on facebook before buying a terroir product in reality, for example I seek opinions about the cooperative" (N°W8); "I go straight to the cooperative's page to see what the community says about it" (N°H6); "with the group 'test in Agadir', it facilitates my search for information and, even to learn some news about a terroir product" (N°M8). We find that the young person consumes not only within a real tribe (Cova and Cova, 2002) but also in another equally large tribe: a digital tribe. These results are in line with those of Mayol (2011), who indicated that online presence has become an important part of contemporary lives, and that we are now witnessing a digital life that is becoming more and more important. For their part, El Kamel and Rigaux-Bricmont (2011) noted that the virtual would also represent a place to express the current quest for authenticity.

Transmission of consumption practices

The analysis of the verbatim showed that the consumption of local products is mainly linked to a family transmission. "...a local product is a habit taken by my family (N°W3); my mother who insisted on taking argane oil with me (N°M3);...during her visit my father often brings me back argane oil (N°M5);...there are dishes that I have been used to taking them with argane oil since my childhood (N°W12)". We explain this resumption of consumption habits by young people as a continuation of their families' practices (Ladwein et al., 2009). As a result, this behavior could be modified or changed

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at a later date. "...when I became independent I allowed myself for example to buy a terroir local product from cooperatives not only from physique person, and not only in bulk, even if my mother often contradicts me" (N°W9). "I've been buying saffron for a long time from public exhibitions and my wife finds it quite effective" (N°M3). In this sense, we would argue that youth and especially with financial independence is a step towards verifying and modifying of consumption's conditions. According to Badot (2004) the youth stage could be a period of change of gestures inherited from the family, or as a phase in which the young consumer would become an actor with personal choices on the culinary scene (Garabuau-Moussaoui, 2002). Changing or maintaining the actions of those around young consumer would remain a transitional step towards the stage of one's own family. "...in my home, I could tell you that I have taken over most of my mother's tricks and techniques, even those I refused before, for example I find the taste of argane oil a little strong, but I give it as even to my little girl because I know that it is very beneficial for her" (N°F10). Our results underline that parents initiate their children's consumption behaviors, at an early age, after, these young consumers maintain them or take them back when they become parents too.

As explained previously, we note that the study lacks depth, certainly, but at this stage, we would learn that the past represents a reason and a result of the quest for authenticity among young consumers. Indeed, even if this young person modifies the characteristics sought in a terroir product, it is, just, a way to continue to consume it and relive the old one. We can compare this practice to the practice of "Do-It-Yourself", named by Camus (2002) by the consumer in order to make this product authentic in his eyes.

In this study, we have focused on the quest for authenticity among young consumers. The data collected show that a terroir product represents an object and a subject of authentic consumption. In this sense, the quest for authenticity would cross the characters of consumption explained by postmodern paradigm. Also, the consumption of a terroir product would seem to be motivated by the satisfaction of a need and the search for a desired self in order to achieve re-enchantment. This reflection is in line with Belk's (1988). The consumption could reflects an existing or desired self, and that in the postmodern era, the two actors in the quest for authenticity would enter into a compromise relationship in order to satisfy it (Cova and Cova, 2002). On a managerial level, we can say that the enhancement of a terroir product requires a consideration of the current quest for authenticity that is also shared by young people. The findings highlight that authenticity is not spontaneously linked to labels but also to other characteristics external to the product itself. Thus, the generational perspective would seem to be interesting to consider in cooperatives' segmentation strategies because its classic

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criteria (age, frequency of purchase, etc.) would now represent a core element to the reality of postmodern consumption.

This paper is not exempt from limits. We recall that the exploratory approach of our research led us to make an unreasonable choice of the sample. Certainly, studies on the generation require significant in-depth study and an intergenerational categorization to understand the motivations of the quest for authenticity for different cohorts while taking into account individual, historical and sociological factors. Thus, the external validity is affected by the chosen terrain. The research focuses on the Moroccan consumer and does not take into account cultural differences.

CONCLUSION

According to Baudrillard (1988), we understand that current times would change societies and their consumption. Consumption would become an object and a subject for contemporaries, which is influenced by the conditions of postmodernity. Taking as an object of research the quest for the authenticity of young people in the context of a terroir product, lets us look at its antecedents and not the staged authenticity. Far from trying to join the debate on the generation and its limits in the postmodern age, our research aimed to mobilize it and to try to understand the relationship between age and the quest for authenticity. This exploratory research points out that:

-The old object is also in demand by young consumers. This quest for authenticity for young consumer would include different features that have their origins in the shift from today's society to postmodernism. The hyper-reality and the assembly of oppositions are the most evoked features. In this sense, the young consumer would be looking for an authentic product with a modern look that is not sophisticated enough.

- Authenticity is a transmitted capital. The quest for the authentic is a weaving of links to the past, generally considered better (Cova and Cova 2002). The results of our study show that young consumers could look for practices and products that they used to consume in childhood under certain conditions. In this sense, we can understand this behaviour as a negotiation of what is transmitted that could be saved as it is or modified. Whatever the form of this transmission, the young consumer hoped for an inter-generational dialogue in order to preserve it, because in a direct or indirect way, he would respond to his quest for authenticity.

Finally, we suggest studying the different Moroccan generations while considering the qualitative and quantitative characteristics. It would also be relevant to question the segmentation strategy of cooperatives under the generational approach. These proposals would make it possible to catch the

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concept of generation, which gives several ways for understanding specific behaviors in Moroccan context.

ANNEXES

Features of study's sample

	Number	Age (years)	
Women	W1	24	Student, medicine
	W2	34	Manager
	W3	30	Administrator
	W4	35	Director, bank
	W5	19	Student, computer science
	W6	20	Student, engineer
	W7	23	Teacher
	W8	22	Student, management
	W9	28	Administrator
	W10	30	Nurse
	W11	25	Teacher
	W12	26	Sales manager
	M1	28	Administrator
	M2	30	Manager
	M3	32	Nurse

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Man	M4	19	Student, management
	M5	20	Student, University
	M6	22	Community manager
	M7	21	Student, engineer
	M8	18	Student, Management

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